

A STUDY OF THE STUDY HABITS OF STUDENTS OF STD IX

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“To acquire knowledge, one must study; but to acquire wisdom, one must observe.”

Marilyn Vos Savant.

Education is a multifaceted course of action consciously planned to impart knowledge and developmental skills. Tutoring is imperative and essential for every person. It is only through teaching and learning that an individual develops one's thoughts, way of interpretation, resourcefulness, expertise, problem solving, morals and ethics and most important one's attitude. Education is the need of the hour for developed as well as developing societies.

As, Dr J S Dhillon states that, “To make the best, the young minds need to be provided opportunities for accessing quality education. Only quality human resources will ensure emergence of a true knowledge society which will ultimately enhance the country's competitiveness in the global economy”.

In this age of competition, study habits have become an important aspect for development and growth in personal, professional, educational, and societal lives of individuals. Educational organizations intend at generating qualitative results, and well educated students who would be prospective nation builders. In order to produce good learners who will excel in various fields Good Study Habits need to be inculcated in the students which will definitely determine one's achievement.

Habits are an everyday practice of behavior that are repeated constantly and tend to take place subconsciously. It is very essential to assist children to build good study habits. If good study habits are accompanied with hard work, focus in the right direction, motivation, enthusiasm and passion for learning, and then this will definitely contribute towards enriching academic skills in students.

According to Garrett, “A habit is the name given to behavior so often repeated as to be automatic.” Burt has aptly stated that, “Habit is an accomplishment form of behavior when things are done quickly, accurately and automatically with little voluntary attention”.

Learning has a vital role in the acquisition of knowledge. Study habits are very important to all human beings who are being educated and are educated. Study habits have a long and lasting and effect on the life of individuals, and it also its effect on the society. Good study habits are a boon it boosts the competency level and saves time and energy as well, it also enhances the confidence level of the students while dealing with others; This enables them to use their spare time for other hobbies and thus see the progress and pleasure in work. On the other hand lack of good study habits affects the students in many ways.

The word study habits comprise of two words - Study and Habits. Study literally means using the intellect to gain knowledge, to be in a state of rapt attention to be enthusiastic and to be conscientious. Habit can best be acquired as it is automatic and mechanical. Study Habits can be described as the actions such as taking notes, holding study groups or even reading that we perform regularly and habitually in order to achieve the long term task of learning. Thus study habits are considered as a medium of learning.

Emphasizing the need to develop in children proper study habits, Locke once remarked that as the child advances in age, he or she frees himself/herself more and more from external restraints and, hence, the best guide and mentor, who can always be at his or her side is the one created in the student's own mind by sound principles and study habits; these habits will decide the destiny of the individual.

Technology has advanced and excellence is the hallmark which every person strives for to obtain success. But unfortunately, there is a major problem in the field of education, as there are a number of failures at the school level. Researchers have conducted researches in the area of study habits. Most of the studies clearly bring out the importance of study habits. Academic institutions set definite principles for the learners, therefore the learners are bound to perform well and rise up to the expected benchmark.

Students need proper guidance for the management of their time and efforts for better prospects. The study habits individually cultivated by them are likely to determine the level of their success. Therefore, in this study, an attempt has been made to find out the study habits of std IX.

Statement of the problem:

A study of the study habits of students of std. IX

Aim of the study:

To study the study habits of students of std IX.

Objective of the study:

To check the study habits of students of std IX.

Design of the study:

The researcher has used the survey method of descriptive type. A Study Habit Questionnaire was used to collect the required data wherein there were seven dimensions:

- Time Management
- Study Environment
- Test Taking/Preparation Skills
- Note taking Skills
- Reading Skills
- Writing Skills
- Math Skills

Sample, sample size and its nature:

The investigator collected data from the students of std IX. The total sample comprised of 70 students. The sample was limited to English medium students. Convenient sampling technique was used to study the study habits of the students of std IX. The sample consisted only of female students.

Analysis technique used for the study:

The investigator made use of descriptive analysis technique to analyse the obtained data. The data has been given a graphical representation.

The table below shows the response of the students to every aspect of the study habits and their position according to their responses

	Great (6-8)	Ok, but improvement needed (3-5)	Needs help here (0-2)
Time Management	38	32	Nil
Study Environment	40	26	4
Test Taking/ Preparation Skills	41	28	1
Note Taking Skills	48	18	4
Reading Skills	33	29	8
Writing Skills	45	23	2
Mathematics	36	23	11

Findings of the study:

It was found that 54% students possess good time management skill and 46% students possess average time management skill.

It was found that 57% students possess good study environment, 37% students possess average study environment and 6% possess poor study environment.

It was found that 59% students possess good test taking/preparation skills, 40% students possess average test taking/preparation skills whereas 1% students possess poor test taking/preparation skills.

It was found that 68% students possess good note taking skills, 26% students needed improvement and 6% students needed help.

It was found that 49% students possess good reading skill, 40% students possess average reading skill whereas 11% students possess poor reading skills.

It was found that 64% students possess good writing skill, 33% students possess average writing skill and 3% students possess poor writing skill.

It was found that 51% students possess good math skill, 33% possess average math skill and 16% possess poor math skill.

Conclusion:

The researcher has come to the following conclusion:

- ❖ 68% students excelled in note taking skills, 26% students needed improvement and 6% were poor.
- ❖ More than half the number had good time management skill; a little less than half the number had average time management.
- ❖ In study environment, test taking and writing skills the students were above 40%, nearly 25% students needed improvement and about 4% needed help.
- ❖ 51% students had good Math skill, 33% were Ok but needed improvement. This was the only skill which had 16% students who were poor and needed help.

The findings of the study revealed the fact that study habits being an important aspect of teaching learning is neglected by both teachers and students. It is the responsibility of the teachers as well as the students to see that they improve their study habits which in turn will help them in their all round development. Therefore it is a must to build up good study habits because, “Motivation is what gets you started. Habit is what keeps you going”. Jim Ryun.

Here are a few tips for cultivating good study habits:

- Chalk out a plan to study with proper time management and follow it sincerely.
- Allot fixed hours for exercise and socializing with friends.
- Select a comfortable area with avoidance of noise and distractions.
- Prepare yourself for different types of tests.
- Form a study group and study for each class everyday.
- Develop an efficient system of note taking.
- Improve your reading habit by selecting good books and read daily with concentration.
- Practise English grammar exercises, punctuation and spellings on a regular basis.

The present investigation will help nation builders with the importance of good study habits. Educational authorities, parents and teachers can play a very important role in improving the study habits among the students.

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